

“KNOWLEDGE MAPPING AND INFORMATION REPACKAGING TOOLS FOR RESEARCHERS: SELECTED TOOLS AN OVERVIEW”

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ABSTRACT:

Summarizing and knowledge mapping tools are most popular tools today. These tools can help identify potential gap in the core research area of your interest. Using these tools, you can easily access the large and complex resources. The knowledge mapping tools uses key word to identify previous documents, and information repackaging tool highlights the information needed in the research paper. Knowledge mapping and information repackaging tools helpful tools for the Researchers to decision making and risk identification of complex resources, Scientists, faculty, and staff and those involved in research. The main aim of this research paper is to be using these tools to save the time of the researchers and convey clear concept of research ideas. The knowledge mapping and information repackaging tools justify the fourth law of library and information science which is “save the time of the users” by dr.S.R.Ranganathan.

KEY WORDS: Knowledge map; Summary Generator; Citation Gecko; Information repackaging.

1.0. INTRODUCTION:

When researchers or academicians dealing with huge amounts of complex information, it is hard to be an expert in every subject. As a result, it makes sense to provide a simple tool for locating individuals with specific abilities within an organization. It not only saves time but also increases efficiency. Nowadays one of the most difficult tasks when

you knew a research area is to know the in-depth knowledge of research area. The Knowledge mapping tools is to help discovery of scientific knowledge. Information is the combination of products and services to meet specific needs. It may be possible by reformatting and synthesizing raw information, combining subject expertise with access to appropriate information sources. Knowledge gaps in facilities management organization and literature reviewed in facilities manag knowledge Mapping - apokmtools. Sites.google.com. (2021). Ement field exhibit trends towards the needs of implementing knowledge mapping. Sink (1991) suggests that performance measurement is “a mystery...complex, frustrating, difficult, challenging, important, abused and misused” function. In the same vein, Alexander (1996) identifies that measuring facilities performance as one of “three essential issues for the effective implementation of a facilities strategy”. These, highlight the rationale and significant of implementing knowledge mapping in the facilities performance evaluation process.

2.0. OBJECTIVES

- To identify the potential gap of core research area
- To know highlights of the research article or paper
- To easy access literature review
- To reduces the researcher’s time
- To know the most up-to-date knowledge to solve a Research challenge

3.0.CONCEPT OF KNOWLEDGE MAPPING:

One of the most important approaches in the field of knowledge management is knowledge mapping. A visual representation of the Academic or company's intellectual capital is a map of information. It aids stakeholders in determining where critical data is stored, how it moves, and any difficulties or gaps. It enables Researchers to concentrate on the most serious outcome of information as well as the most fruitful knowledge prospects. Knowledge mapping and information repackaging is the most effective tools for Academicians & industrialists to preserve their expertise and detect knowledge gaps that are limiting their growth, impeding market possibilities, or causing failures. Mapping can be used in several research and information seeking activities and thus could become more central to library instruction. For example, maps could be used more fully in online teaching and learning. In addition to using maps to illustrate specific information literacy concepts, Librarians could use conceptual maps to structure student navigation through information literacy tutorials and student quizzes could be constructed around having students correctly fill in labels that represent accurate relationships among concepts (Edwards and Cooper 2010; Pepper 2006; Pinto, Doucette, and Fernandez-Ramos 2010).

4.0.WHAT IS KNOWLEDGE MAPPING?

Knowledge mapping is a user's understanding or awareness of a subject obtained via learning or experience. The optimum form of data that is beneficial for evaluating the meaning is known as information. Knowledge, on the other hand, is the information that is both relevant and objective and makes a difference.

5.0.NEED OF THE STUDY:

Thus, it detects and clarifies the importance of the knowledge to attain planned goals in an exceedingly easier and friendly approach. Information presented within the knowledge map it helps researchers to look at previous research issues and find out ideas in the interested research topic. Constructing summarizing and knowledge mapping helps to researchers to create up and increase training and academic support system to attain successfully their research work. These tools can be using a single key word present the multi-disciplinary subject's contents.

6.0 KNOWLEDGE MAPPING TOOLS:

Citation gecko, Open Knowledge mapping, My science work, Mind Maps, Competency Mapping, Concept Maps, Topic Map, Mind Manager, etc. In this study I selected these three tools which are Citation Gecko, Open Knowledge map and my Science Work most useful tools for the researchers.

6.1. CITATION GECKO:

Citation gecko is here to assist you to the foremost relevant papers to your research and provides you to more complete sense of the of research landscape. Start from a tiny low set of 'seed papers' that outline a locality you're interested. Gecko will search the citation network for connected papers allowing you to quickly identify important papers you will have missed Gecko knowledge mapping tools unique feature is identifying and shows the year wise research gap in the research core area.

6.1.2. HOW TO SEARCH

- Open citation gecko through your browser
- Add seed papers that define your area of interest and Gecko will find you connected papers.
- Enter key word in search dialogue
- Display your key word related papers titles
- Select your title & Click on Add selected as seed paper
- Then it will show you year wise like below image and click any one of dot that will take you to original article.

Image 1: Citation gecko

6.2. OPEN KNOWLEDGE MAPPING:

It is a free online open access knowledge mapping tool visual interface to world scientific knowledge is to revolutionize discovery of scientific knowledge. Norway day's research is increases in the all fields. This site is believed that a better way to explore and discover scientific knowledge will benefit to all kind of researchers not only for academic level. This tool helps you to identifying relevant concepts, irrelevant your search and find opens content. When you search a single content show you multi-disciplinary fields. In this tool we can also access PubMed (Life Science Database) and other all disciplines open access papers. The full text is only click and single click you can access.

6.2.1. YOU CAN FILTER YOUR SEARCH OPTIONS:

All time/last month/last year and most relevant or most recent and also Document type- Audio or Books or both these are the options refine your search.

Image 2: Open Knowledge Mapping

7.0. WHAT IS INFORMATION REPACKAGING (SUMMARIZING)?

Information repackaging is considered as a process of information from a relatively longer articles, theory, or write-up and consolidating into smaller version that includes all the original facts and important ideas. Writing a 3 to 4 sentences explanation that includes all the important elements of a thesis or research paper is example for repackaging.

Information repackaging tools are SMMRY, Summary generator, Automatic text summarizer, Summary, Online summarizer, Paper Digest, etc. there are so many summering tools but I have selected two tools which is most suitable for researchers those are SMMRY and Automatic text summarizing.

7.1. SMMRY:

SMMRY (pronounced as SUMMARY) was created to summarize articles and text. SMMRY's mission is to provide an efficient manner of understanding text, which is done primarily by reducing the text to only the most important sentences. SMMRY accomplishes its mission by: Ranking sentences by importance using core algorithm, rearranging the summary to focus on a topic; by selection of a key word, removing transition phrases. Removing unnecessary clauses, removing excessive examples. There are seven simple steps to summarizes are follows

1. Associate word with their grammatical counter parts. (e.g. "city" and "cities")
2. Calculate the occurrence of each word in the text.
3. Assign each word with points depending on their popularity.
4. Detect which periods represent the end of sentence. (e.g. "Mr." does not")
5. Split up the text into individual sentences.
6. Rank sentences by the sum of their words' points.
7. Return X of the most highly ranked sentences in chronological order.

Image 3: SMMRY

In the above image uploaded text and below image shows the important facts from the text.

Image 4: SMMRY

7.2. AUTOMATIC TEXT SUMMARIZER:

Automatic text summarizer is a multi- language summarizing and paraphrasing artificial intelligence repackaging tool for text articles, extracting the most important sentences, and ranking a sentence based on importance. In this tool upload your text in its dialog box and click on the summarize button then it summarize and shows the important facts like shown in below image.

Image 5: Automatic text Summarizer**8.0. CONCLUSION:**

Start with a knowledge map to start capturing your knowledge. Knowledge mapping, unlike an information report, is a method of visualizing a research institutes or organization's more detailed knowledge. As a result, while dealing with complex issues, it's critical to create a knowledge map. Making an eye-catching mind map simply takes a few minutes with the various mind map themes and solutions available. in this paper is to gives you an overview of the knowledge mapping and information repackaging tools tools. The knowledge mapping is a way to visualize a clear concept of researchers to more in- depth knowledge. I have selected two knowledge mapping and two information repackaging tools. These tools help to the researchers to decision making and improves your efficiency to create a new idea and increase the research productivity.

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